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Military Preparedness of India in Response to China: A Comparative Study between UPA and NDA Government

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ABSTRACT

India and China share lots of similarities. They both express joy in, and relate to, the inheritances of their long-lasting civilizations. Both are nuclear haves with world class military capabilities. Beside the benefits of their growing economies both are grappling with the domestic contradictions and upheavals of their billion strong citizens. Their relationship, though marked by frequent military face-offs and periodic tensions along their lengthy disputed border, can be best described as 'purposeful and stable. The relationship between India and China became pragmatic in UPA and more pragmatic in NDA rule. This article is an attempt to make a comparative study between UPA and NDA Government programmes and policies regarding Indo-China relations.

KEY WORDS: UPA, NDA, Ministry of Defence, Missiles, Technology Centric Approach

INTRODUCTION:

India and China share lots of similarities. They both express joy in, and relate to, the inheritances of their long-lasting civilizations. Both are nuclear haves with world class military capabilities. Beside the benefits of their growing economies both are grappling with the domestic contradictions and upheavals of their billion strong citizens. In quest of their national aspirations both are jostling for their equitable positions in the world order. If India closely watches China's rise, China is equally aware of India's growing influence. Despite being strong trading partners, they see each other as strategic rivals, frequently clashing in global affairs. (Hsiang: 2008) Their relationship, though marked by frequent military face-offs and periodic tensions along their lengthy disputed border, can be best described as 'purposeful and stable. The relationship between India and China became pragmatic in UPA and more pragmatic in NDA rule. To be pragmatic military preparedness is essential. Military dependence on others makes our foreign policy dependent upon others

especially on western powers. So, previous two and present NDA government are trying to make more progress on military preparedness to put a check on Chinese aggressive policy.

Military Preparedness of India under UPA Government:

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During Manmohan Singh's tenure as part of the UPA government from 2004 to 2014, India acquired a diverse range of military platforms and equipment, amounting to over \$30 billion, from 17 different countries. These acquisitions included various contracts with countries such as France, Israel, Russia, and the United States. Over the course of a decade, the UPA government entered into 142 defense contracts, covering a wide spectrum of military assets.

These acquisitions included combat, transport, and trainer aircraft; medium-lift and surveillance helicopters; main battle tanks (MBTs); infantry combat vehicles; an aircraft carrier; landing dock platforms; diesel-electric submarines; frigates; and a variety of missiles, rockets, specialized ammunition, radar systems, engines, and miscellaneous ordnance for all three branches of the armed forces. The total estimated value of these procurements was around \$3 billion. (Sali:2013)

Following the election of Modi government, which first took office in May 2014 and again elected in 2019, several tenders those were in the final stage of negotiation during the previous government were gradually finalized and implemented. These acquisitions included:

- 1. AH-64E Apache Attack Helicopters:** The Indian military has enhanced its capabilities with the purchase and subsequent induction of 22 AH-64E Apache attack helicopters.
- 2. Chinook CH-47F Heavy-Lift Helicopters:** The procurement of 15 Chinook CH-47F heavy-lift helicopters for the Indian armed forces.
- 3. BAE Systems M777 Howitzers:** The Indian military is enhancing its artillery capabilities with the acquisition of 145 BAE Systems M777 155mm/39-caliber lightweight howitzers.
- 4. Leasing of Russian Akula-class Submarine:** In 2025, the Indian Navy will acquire its second leased Project 971 'Akula'-class nuclear-powered submarine from Russia, known as the 'Schuka-B.'

Additionally, the Modi government also pursued add-on purchases of various military equipment initiated by the UPA government. These included both fixed-wing and rotary-wing platforms, unarmed and un-manned aerial vehicles (UAVs), missiles, and other gear. Numerous earlier initiated upgrades of in-service equipment were also being processed during this period.

These efforts aimed to modernize and enhance India's military capabilities across various domains. (Richards:2015)

During the UPA's tenure, there was notable progress in several domestic defense programs. These included:

- 1. Ballistic Missile Submarine (SSBN) Project:** The UPA government made significant strides in the development of ballistic missile submarines, a crucial component of India's nuclear triad. These submarines are capable of carrying ballistic missiles armed with nuclear warheads.
- 2. Local Manufacture of Medium Transport Aircraft (MTA):** The UPA government initiated the local production of Airbus Defence and Space's medium transport aircraft through a technology transfer arrangement with a private sector vendor. This program aimed to enhance India's indigenous manufacturing capabilities in the defense sector.
- 3. Exclusion of HAL in MTA Deal:** Notably, Defense Minister A.K. Antony's Ministry of Defence intentionally excluded the state-run Hindustan Aeronautics Limited (HAL) from a deal to supply 56 MTAs to the Indian Air Force (IAF). This move sought to encourage private sector participation and competition in defense manufacturing, diversifying the sources of military equipment.

These initiatives reflect the UPA government's commitment to advancing domestic defense capabilities, fostering indigenous production, and encouraging private sector participation in the defense industry.

Despite significant pressure from Hindustan Aeronautics Limited (HAL) to secure the contract, the Ministry of Defence (MoD) under the UPA government stood firm in its decision to award the contract for C295 MW transports to a Tata-led consortium. This decision persisted for nearly 12 years before being finalized in September. This contract not only ensured the procurement of essential military aircraft but also paved the way for an expanded role for private manufacturers in the indigenous production of military aircraft. The UPA government's commitment to encouraging private sector participation in defense manufacturing was reaffirmed through this contract award.

According to SIPRI, India made significant acquisitions of over six hundred aircraft and helicopters across the three military services during the period of

2004-2014. Notable among these acquisitions for the Indian Air Force (IAF) were approximately 250 Sukhoi Su-30MKI multi-role fighters, which were produced under license by HAL. The IAF also acquired 6 numbers of Lockheed Martin C-130J-30 'Hercules' and 10 numbers of Boeing C-17 Globemaster-III transport aircraft, along with three Israel Aircraft Industries Phalcon Ilyushin-76TD airborne early warning and control (AEW&C) aircraft.

In subsequent years, the IAF expanded its capabilities with the procurement of 11 additional C-17s, making it one of the largest operators of this types of aircraft, second only to the US Air Force. During the UPA government's tenure, the IAF also acquired 75 Swiss Pilatus PC-7 Mk II tandem-seat basic trainer aircraft, 151 Mil Mi-17V5 'Hip' medium lift helicopters, and a range of other rotary and fixed-wing platforms in smaller numbers.

Additionally, the UPA government's Ministry of Defence (MoD) entered into contracts for the upgrade of the IAF's fleet of 51 French Mirage-2000H 'Vajra' fighters, which played a pivotal role in the Balakot air strike against some militant camps in Pakistan in 2019, February. The MoD also initiated the upgrade of approximately 60 MiG-29 Fulcrum-A combat aircraft, although these upgrades have not yet been fully completed. These acquisitions and upgrades significantly enhanced the IAF's operational capabilities during the UPA era.

During the UPA administration, the Indian Navy (IN) made significant acquisitions to enhance its maritime capabilities. This included the procurement of 8 numbers of P-8I Poseidon multi-mission maritime reconnaissance aircraft equipped with anti-submarine warfare capabilities. The IN also added 28 warships to its fleet during this period.

One of the most notable acquisitions was the acquisition and refurbishment of INS Vikramaditya (formerly Admiral Gorshkov), a massive 46,000-tonne aircraft carrier from Russia. This carrier came equipped with a complement of 16 MiG-29K fighter aircraft. (Alam:2015)

Following this purchase, the IN proceeded to procure an additional 29 similar fighters to complement the home-grown Aircraft Carrier-1, programmed for commissioning as INS Vikrant in August 2022. These acquisitions significantly expanded the IN's capabilities and strengthened its presence in the region.

Under the UPA administration, the Indian Navy initiated several key acquisitions to enhance its naval capabilities. These acquisitions included:

1. Procurement of six French Scorpene diesel-electric submarines (SSKs), which were intended for license-building at the Mazagon Dock Shipbuilders. Four of these submarines had already been commissioned, significantly bolstering the IN's submarine fleet.
2. Acquisition of INS Jalashwa (formerly USS Trenton), a second-hand 16,900-tonne Austin-class landing dock platform or troop ship. This vessel was capable of accommodating six UH-3H Sea King helicopters, further expanding the IN's amphibious capabilities.
3. Purchase of six Talwar-class Project 11356 frigates, which added to the IN's surface fleet and provided enhanced naval firepower.
4. Procurement of 6-8 Kamov Ka-28 and Ka-31 'Helix' Airborne Early Warning and Control (AEW&C) helicopters, which played a vital role in naval surveillance and reconnaissance operations.
5. Upgrading of Ilyushin 38D four-engine turboprop maritime patrol aircraft, enhancing the IN's maritime patrol and anti-submarine warfare capabilities.

These acquisitions collectively strengthened the IN's capabilities and contributed to its role as a potent maritime force in the region.

During the UPA administration, the Indian Army (IA) underwent significant upgrades and acquisitions to enhance its ground capabilities. These acquisitions included:

1. Procurement of over 1,000 T90S Main Battle Tanks (MBTs), with a substantial number being license-built at Heavy Vehicles Factory in Avadi, Chennai, under technology transfer agreements. These modern MBTs provided a significant boost to the IA's armored capabilities.
2. Acquisition of 123 Russian BMP-2 infantry fighting vehicles, which played a crucial role in infantry support and combat operations.
3. Purchase of wide range long, medium, and short-range missiles, including the versatile Israeli surface-to-air Barak missile system. These missiles enhanced the IA's air defense capabilities, providing protection against various aerial threats.

These acquisitions strengthened the IA's ground forces and contributed to its readiness and effectiveness in various operational scenarios.

During the UPA administration, several critical defense projects were advanced and completed, including:

- 1. INS Arihant:** India's first indigenously designed and built nuclear-powered ballistic missile submarine (SSBN) was launched in 2009 and secretly commissioned in August 2016. The INS Arihant represented a significant milestone in India's strategic nuclear capabilities.
- 2. Arjun Main Battle Tank (MBT):** The UPA government played a role in fast-tracking the stalled Arjun MBT project. The Arjun MBT is a domestically developed and manufactured tank that has been integrated into the Indian Army's armored formations.
- 3. Tejas Light Combat Aircraft (LCA):** India's light combat aircraft, Tejas project was also expedited during the UPA era. The Tejas is India's indigenously developed and manufactured fighter aircraft, enhancing the Indian Air Force's (IAF) combat capabilities.

These projects showcased the UPA government's commitment to advancing indigenous defense capabilities, including submarines, tanks, and fighter aircraft, to strengthen India's defense preparedness.

The UPA government also played a significant role in advancing missile technology and artillery capabilities in India. Some notable achievements during that period include:

- 1. BrahMos Cruise Missile:** The UPA government furthered the development of the BrahMos missile, which is known as the world's fastest cruise missile. Its high speed and stealthy nature make it virtually undetectable, enhancing India's offensive capabilities.
- 2. Dhanush Howitzer:** India initiated the local manufacturing of Dhanush, upgraded version of the Bofors FH-77B 155mm/39-caliber towed howitzer. Originally, India had imported 410 of these howitzers from Sweden in 1986-87. However, due to a corruption scandal, the transfer of technology to license-build them was delayed for years. Eventually, the Indian Army initiated a project to indigenously build guns with a longer 45-caliber barrel to extend

their strike range. The Dhanush is now set to enter series production to fulfill a 2018 order for 114 guns.

These developments demonstrate the UPA government's efforts to enhance India's military capabilities, including advanced missile systems and artillery, to strengthen its defense infrastructure and readiness.

Above all, the UPA government achieved significant progress in encouraging the active participation of private sectors in strengthening India's industries for Defense. This initiative aimed to reduce the monopoly of the nine state-owned defense public sector units and the extensive Ordnance Factory Board, which has subsequently been transformed into a corporatized entity. According to a defense analyst, "While the defense sector was initially opened to private manufacturers under Vajpayee's government in 2001, it experienced substantial growth during the decade-long UPA administration, ultimately bearing greater fruit after 2014." The analyst preferred to remain anonymous due to the sensitive nature of the topic.

The UPA administration appeared to have downplayed the critical issue of the Indian Army's severe ammunition shortages, a matter that was starkly emphasized by the Comptroller and Auditor General in May 2015. According to the CAG report at the time, not only was the Indian Army grappling with a dire scarcity of ammunition, but even its wastage reserves, essential for sustaining supplies over a 40-day war, had dwindled to just 20 days. In the fiscal year ending in March 2013, which was the second-to-last year of the UPA's tenure, the CAG spotlighted a deficit in 125 out of 170 types of tank, artillery, and small arms ammunitions. Subsequently, this situation saw improvement through the involvement of the private sector.

Military Preparedness of India under NDA Government:

The current NDA government's unwavering dedication to strengthening the Indian armed forces and border security agencies is clearly demonstrated by its strategic efforts to equip them with cutting-edge technology and equipment. These initiatives encompass a wide range of modern tools, including advanced surveillance technology, state-of-the-art communication systems, cutting-edge weaponry, and specialized vehicles. The underlying objective of these endeavors is to bolster

India's defense capabilities, elevate its state of readiness, and ensure a well-rounded response to emerging threats.

Under the leadership of Modi, the government has taken a proactive stance in addressing existing limitations by implementing transformative measures and embarking on modernization initiatives within the Indian military. A crucial facet of these reforms involves promoting greater collaboration and jointness among different branches of the military. This collaborative approach enhances interoperability and synergies, enabling more efficient resource utilization and the capacity to effectively tackle multifaceted challenges.

A central element of the government's transformative strategy is the establishment of four theater commands. These commands are strategically designed to facilitate seamless cooperation and resource-sharing among various branches of the military, thereby enabling a more integrated and synchronized response to threats along India's borders with Pakistan and China. These initiatives underscore India's steadfast commitment to aligning its military infrastructure with the demands of modern challenges.

However, the urgency of modernization is particularly evident in the context of countering Chinese border aggression. While the ongoing reform efforts are undeniably crucial, India's successful deterrence strategy relies on swiftly adopting advanced defense technologies. To achieve this, a focused approach is imperative, especially in increasing funding allocations for equipment acquisition and maintenance. As India continues to advance its indigenous defense manufacturing capabilities, it is essential to concurrently address immediate defense requirements, many of which can be effectively met through foreign acquisitions.

The Indian government's unwavering commitment to strengthening defense capabilities by adopting cutting-edge technologies is evident in its efforts to equip the armed forces and border security agencies with advanced tools. These reform initiatives, such as promoting jointness and creating theater commands, demonstrate a proactive and future-oriented approach. However, the urgency to rapidly integrate sophisticated defense technologies and allocate the required funds for equipment acquisition highlights the immediate need to effectively deter potential threats.

This dual approach, which combines immediate foreign purchases with long-term goals of indigenous manufacturing, plays a pivotal role in ensuring that India

maintains a comprehensive and robust defense posture. It allows India to address its immediate security concerns while also working towards self-reliance in defense production for the future.

The Indian government's proactive stance towards bolstering its defense capabilities is evident in its comprehensive strategic procurement plans across various branches of the armed forces. These initiatives place a strong emphasis on indigenous design and development, aiming to promote self-reliance and fortify the nation's defense infrastructure. In line with this forward-looking agenda, the Indian Army is prioritizing the acquisition of vital assets, including Rough Terrain Fork Lift Trucks (RTFLT), Bridge Laying Tanks (BLTs), Wheeled Armoured Fighting Vehicles (Wh AFVs) equipped with Anti-Tank Guided Missiles (ATGMs), and Weapon Locating Radars (WLRs).

The significant focus on procuring these equipment domestically underscores India's steadfast commitment to nurturing indigenous capabilities. By fostering a robust ecosystem for domestic design and development, the Indian Army is not only addressing immediate procurement needs but also laying a solid foundation for long-term self-sufficiency in critical military assets. This approach aligns with India's vision for a self-reliant and technologically advanced defense sector.

The Indian Navy's ambitious modernization journey encompasses the acquisition of Next Generation Corvettes (NGCs), a substantial investment estimated at Rs 36,000 crore. These NGCs are versatile assets capable of performing a range of critical operational roles, including surveillance, escort missions, deterrence, Surface Action Group (SAG) maneuvers, Search & Attack operations, and Coastal Defense. Leveraging innovative in-house design and advanced shipbuilding technology, the Navy is set to elevate India's maritime prowess to unprecedented levels. (Muratbekova:2017).

Furthermore, the NGCs are in perfect harmony with the government's comprehensive 'Security and Growth for all in the Region' (SAGAR) initiative, playing a pivotal role in enhancing regional stability and prosperity. In the pursuit of defense indigenization, the esteemed Navratna CPSE, Hindustan Aeronautics Limited (HAL), has been entrusted with pivotal responsibilities. By engaging in the production of Dornier aircraft and Su-30 MKI aero-engines, HAL is strongly aligned with India's quest for self-reliance in defense. Through its concerted efforts in the aero-engine

material domain, HAL is poised to make substantial contributions to the nation's defense ecosystem. This collaborative endeavor is poised to strengthen India's defense infrastructure, promote self-sufficiency, and bolster its strategic capabilities.

The Defense Acquisition Council (DAC) has taken a holistic approach, emphasizing not only the acquisition of new equipment but also embracing digital transformation as a pivotal aspect of modernizing the defense sector. One of the most noteworthy endeavors in this regard is the 'Digital Coast Guard' project, which has received authorization under the 'Buy (Indian) Category.' This visionary project serves as a prime example of how the DAC is steering the armed forces into the digital age.

The 'Digital Coast Guard' initiative is set to revolutionize the Indian Coast Guard by envisioning the establishment of a secure, nationwide network. This network will act as the backbone for the digital transformation of various Coast Guard operations, including surface and aviation maneuvers, logistics, financial management, and human resources. It is a groundbreaking endeavor aimed at enhancing the efficiency, effectiveness, and responsiveness of the Coast Guard's mission-critical functions.

This transformative initiative seamlessly aligns with the government's broader vision of establishing a digitally advanced defense framework for the country. It underscores the government's commitment to leveraging cutting-edge technology to bolster national security.

The Indian government's approach to defense procurement is multifaceted, emphasizing both indigenous development and strategic advancement. This approach spans across various branches of the armed forces, ensuring that each receives the necessary resources and capabilities to fulfill its mission.

For the Army, this entails the development of ground-based assets that are not only state-of-the-art but also produced domestically, reducing reliance on foreign suppliers. In the case of the Navy, the focus is on acquiring cutting-edge maritime technology to strengthen naval capabilities and protect India's extensive coastline and maritime interests.

Furthermore, the government's commitment to aero-engine indigenization underscores its dedication to achieving self-reliance in critical areas of defense

technology. This initiative aims to reduce dependence on foreign suppliers for aero-engines, a crucial component of military aircraft.

In essence, these diverse initiatives collectively bolster India's defense preparedness, foster self-reliance, and showcase the nation's technological prowess on the global stage. Through a blend of indigenous development and digital transformation, India is actively shaping a modern and formidable defense force capable of meeting the challenges of the 21st century.

On August 15, 2019, Prime Minister Modi made a momentous announcement that reverberated as a profoundly positive stride in India's defense sector. He declared the intention to establish the position of Chief of Defence Staff (CDS) by the end of that year. This announcement, according to Admiral Arun Prakash, a distinguished former Chief of Naval Staff, was nothing short of historic and represented the "most significant development in the national security domain since Independence."

The creation of the CDS role came with a paramount mission – to cultivate a sense of unity and collaboration among the diverse branches of the Indian military. This visionary move aimed to transcend traditional silos and hierarchies, fostering a more cohesive and synchronized approach to national defense. Central to the CDS's mandate was the establishment of joint theatre commands. These commands would serve as crucial operational entities, bringing together the Army, Navy, Air Force, and potentially other specialized units under a unified leadership structure. This integration would not only optimize resource utilization but also enhance the effectiveness and responsiveness of India's military capabilities.

In essence, the formation of the CDS position signaled a transformative shift in India's defense strategy. It reflected a proactive approach to address the complex and evolving security challenges of the 21st century. By promoting unity, synergy, and joint operations, the CDS role aimed to ensure that India's armed forces would be better prepared to safeguard the nation's interests and respond effectively to a wide range of security threats. This decision underscored the government's commitment to modernizing the country's defense apparatus and strengthening its position on the global stage.

The appointment of a Chief of Defence Staff (CDS) marked a significant milestone in the journey towards

achieving greater jointness within the Indian military. Its importance lay in its potential to bridge the gaps that traditionally existed between the different service branches, facilitating their ability to operate seamlessly and effectively towards common strategic objectives. Notably, the directive to establish joint theatre commands aimed to take this collaboration to the next level, streamlining military operations and capitalizing on the synergies among the various branches.

However, it's worth acknowledging that the creation of the CDS and the pursuit of jointness within the Indian military did not come without its complexities and challenges. Within the ranks of the Indian military services, differing opinions emerged regarding the necessity of such a position and the most effective model of achieving jointness. These debates often reflected the unique cultures, traditions, and operational doctrines of each service branch.

Despite the disagreements and complexities, the importance of this initiative could not be underestimated, especially when considering the evolving global military landscape. Modern militaries around the world have recognized the value of integrated theatre commands as a means to enhance coordination, interoperability, and strategic agility. Such commands allow for more efficient utilization of resources, quicker decision-making, and a more effective response to a wide range of security challenges, including traditional and asymmetric threats.

In a rapidly changing world, where security threats are becoming increasingly complex and interconnected, the need for a unified and collaborative military approach is paramount. The creation of the CDS and the pursuit of jointness within the Indian military reflect a forward-thinking strategy aimed at ensuring the nation's defense forces remain agile, adaptable, and ready to address the challenges of the 21st century. While the road to full jointness may be marked by challenges and differences of opinion, the overarching goal of a more integrated and effective military is a vision that holds great promise for India's national security and defense capabilities.

Prime Minister Modi's visionary approach underscored the critical importance of fostering unity and cooperation within the Indian military establishment. The appointment of the Chief of Defence Staff (CDS) was a strategic move aimed at transcending individual service interests, with a strong emphasis on the collective strength that emerges from joint efforts. This decision

symbolized a departure from traditional silos and highlighted the value of a cohesive and synchronized military approach.

The directive to establish joint theatre commands was recognition of the imperative to adapt to contemporary military practices and fully harness India's defense capabilities. It reflected an understanding that in an ever-changing global security landscape, effective collaboration and coordination among the service branches are essential for addressing multifaceted and dynamic challenges.

Prime Minister Modi's announcement to create the CDS position and implement joint theatre commands represented a pivotal moment in India's defense landscape. While it's true that challenges and differing opinions persisted, this move showcased India's unwavering commitment to enhancing military integration. It aligned the nation with global trends and emphasized the importance of leveraging the synergies among its service branches.

This endeavor holds great promise for fortifying India's defense capabilities and preparedness for the challenges of the future. By fostering a culture of cooperation and jointness, India can enhance its ability to respond effectively to a wide range of security threats, uphold its national interests, and play a more influential role on the global stage. Prime Minister Modi's forward-looking approach in this regard demonstrates a commitment to securing the nation's future while adapting to the evolving dynamics of modern warfare.

The reform initiative undertaken went well beyond the pursuit of jointness within the Indian military and encompassed a broader and more transformative scope. At the heart of this endeavor was a concerted effort to reshape the dynamics between the Ministry of Defence (MoD) and the armed services. The historically complex landscape of civil-military relations, which had often been regarded as a stumbling block in India's defense policymaking, emerged as a focal point for substantial transformation.

In response to the need for reform, the government made an unexpected and audacious move by creating a new entity known as the Department of Military Affairs (DMA) within the MoD. This department would be led by the Chief of Defence Staff (CDS), marking a significant departure from the traditional power dynamics between the civilian and military leadership.

This bold step signaled the government's unwavering commitment to revamping the traditionally intricate relationship between the military and the civilian leadership. The interplay between the MoD and the armed services, often considered a persistent challenge, was now poised for a paradigm shift. The introduction of the DMA, under the leadership of the CDS, represented a groundbreaking development in this regard.

Under this innovative arrangement, specific civilian officials within the MoD would find themselves working under the guidance and direction of the CDS. This shift in authority and responsibility was a clear departure from the status quo and marked a profound change in the way decisions were made and policies were formulated within the defense establishment.

The creation of the DMA, led by the CDS, exemplified the government's commitment to streamlining decision-making processes, enhancing coordination, and fostering a more collaborative approach between the military and civilian sectors of the defense apparatus. This transformation aimed to eliminate bottlenecks and bureaucratic hurdles, allowing for more efficient and effective governance in matters of national security. (Mishra:2020)

In sum, the establishment of the DMA and the empowerment of the CDS within the MoD represented a pivotal moment in India's defense policymaking. It reflected a forward-thinking approach to addressing longstanding challenges and strengthening the nation's defense capabilities by promoting greater synergy between civilian and military leadership. This innovative move held the potential to reshape the landscape of India's defense governance and further enhance its preparedness to meet the complex security challenges of the modern era.

The strategic rationale underpinning this innovation was highly compelling. Delegating significant authority to the Chief of Defence Staff (CDS) across various military domains held the potential to rectify long-standing structural deficiencies in civil-military relations. Through the consolidation of decision-making processes and the streamlining of communication channels under the stewardship of the CDS, the government sought to surmount historical obstacles that often impeded the effective formulation and execution of policies.

In essence, the establishment of the Department of Military Affairs (DMA) under the leadership of the CDS

heralded a transformative and forward-thinking approach. The restructuring was designed to rebalance the distribution of power between the military and civilian leadership, dismantling barriers and fostering a more cohesive and collaborative decision-making process. This reimagined framework not only promised enhanced efficiency but also ignited a fresh spirit of collaboration that had the potential to open new avenues for bolstering India's defense capabilities. (Harsh and Mankikar: 2024)

The scope of the reform initiative extended far beyond the promotion of jointness; it encompassed a comprehensive overhaul of civil-military relations. The creation of the Department of Military Affairs within the Ministry of Defence represented a bold step towards nurturing greater unity and more effective cooperation between the military and civilian leadership. By addressing structural weaknesses and realigning decision-making processes, this innovative approach aimed to elevate India's defense policymaking and enhance its strategic preparedness for the future

Amidst the backdrop of significant strategic advancements, there is an increasingly pronounced focus on the integration of cutting-edge technologies within the military landscape. This forward-looking approach encompasses a broad spectrum of technologies, ranging from robotics and artificial intelligence to autonomous systems, and includes pivotal domains like space and cyber operations. The amalgamation of these emerging technologies holds the potential to reshape the very dynamics of warfare, challenging conventional assumptions and fundamentally altering the conduct of military operations.

Under the dynamic leadership of Prime Minister Modi, the Indian government has shown unwavering determination in propelling the adoption of these emerging technologies by the armed forces. These innovations possess the transformative potential to enhance the speed, reach, and effectiveness of military operations, effectively rewriting the playbook of strategic engagement. Recognizing the game-changing potential inherent in these advancements, the government has actively encouraged the Indian armed forces to embrace these technologies and develop new capabilities.

A testament to this commitment was the elevation of defense cyber and space agencies to the status of independent tri-service entities. This strategic move was

meticulously orchestrated to ensure seamless coordination of operations within these critical domains. By facilitating strategic synchronization, the government aims to harness the advantages of cyber and space capabilities in tandem with conventional military strength.

This integration of new technologies and capabilities represents a pivotal shift, steering the Indian armed forces away from a traditionally ‘personnel-intensive’ framework and towards a modern ‘technology-centric’ approach. The potential benefits are manifold, including improved situational awareness, enhanced precision, and increased operational flexibility. As India embraces the era of tech-driven warfare, the nation’s defense forces stand poised to adapt, innovate, and thrive in an ever-evolving and complex global security landscape.

This transition, driven by the visionary approach of the Modi Government, represents a significant evolution in India’s defense strategy. It not only bolsters the preparedness and effectiveness of the armed forces but also underscores the forward-looking trajectory of India’s military readiness. With a vigilant eye on the evolving landscape of modern warfare, the Indian military has been diligently assessing the practicality of emerging technologies on today’s battlefields. However, the paramount challenge lies in harnessing the untapped potential of these technologies and turning it into tangible capabilities. The current imperative revolves around the effective implementation of these technologies, requiring seamless integration, rigorous training, and strategic execution. (Singh:2017)

The strategic push towards adopting emerging technologies signifies a fundamental shift in India’s defense perspective. Under the leadership of Prime Minister Modi’s government, there has been a staunch advocacy for embracing these technologies, recognizing their potential to significantly enhance operational effectiveness. By establishing tri-service entities dedicated to defense cyber and space operations and promoting a technology-centric military approach, India positions itself to navigate the intricate future of warfare with strategic foresight and technological prowess.

CONCLUSION:

This transformative journey not only fortifies India’s defense posture but also reaffirms the nation’s commitment to staying at the forefront of military innovation. It underscores the adaptability of the Indian armed forces in response to emerging threats and

challenges from the Chinese side. As the world grapples with the complexities of modern security dynamics, India’s pursuit of cutting-edge technologies reflects its determination to remain a formidable and agile force on the global stage. Through this strategic evolution, India is well-equipped to safeguard its interests and uphold its national security in an ever-changing world.

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